

Local Government in Ethiopia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Zemelak Ayele

CFGs - Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies
Addis Ababa University

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Ethiopia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Addis Ababa University: Zemelak Ayele
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Daggy J Ali_Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Ethiopia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Ethiopia: An Introduction	8
2.2. <i>Autonomy of Local Governments</i>	11
2.3. <i>Sanitation and Hygiene Service Delivery in Urban Local Governments: A Federally Integrated Practice</i>	18
2.4. <i>Responsibilities for and Practices of Urban Land Use Planning in the City of Adama</i>	25
2.5. <i>Solid Waste Management in the City of Bahir Dar: A Matter of Capacity and Public Awareness</i> ...	34
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Ethiopia: An Introduction	39
3.2. <i>The Fiscal Equalization Scheme for Woredas</i>	43
3.3. <i>Financing Municipal Services</i>	46
3.4. <i>Financing Healthcare: The Example of the Raya-Kobo District</i>	49
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Ethiopia: An Introduction.....	55
4.2. <i>The Practice of Local Government Creation (Splitting)</i>	57
4.3. <i>Amalgamating Five Special Local Governments into a Single Administrative Zone vs Self-Government Rights of Ethnic Groups in SNNPRS</i>	61
4.4. <i>Splitting Local Government and its (Un)expected Outcomes: The Case of Amhara National Regional State</i>	67
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Ethiopia: An Introduction	73
5.2. <i>Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations</i>	75
5.3. <i>Changing Urban Place Names in Post 2018 Amhara National Regional State: The View from Bahir Dar City</i>	85
5.4. <i>Infrastructure Projects in Addis Ababa: Between Self-Government of the Capital City and Federal Intervention</i>	91
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Ethiopia: An Introduction	96
6.2. <i>Participation in Urban Water Management Board in Adama/Oromia</i>	99
6.3. <i>Local Governance and Gender in Family Relations</i>	104
6.4. <i>Political Participation Along Ethnic Lines: The City of Dire Dawa</i>	108

Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Ethiopia: An Introduction

Yilkal Ayalew Workneh, *Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies, Addis Ababa University*

When the DLDP was launched by the federal government in 2001, the role of local governments became crucial and their mandate broadened.¹¹¹ Since 2001, two aspects of decentralization have taken place in Ethiopia: introduction of regular local government level block grants and their splitting. The splitting practices resulted in a dramatic increment of *regular local governments* throughout the country. By 2013, the number of such local government units had increased by 31 per cent from 2001.¹¹² On the contrary, ethnic local governments stayed constant in number.¹¹³ In this scenario, urban administrations with *woreda* (district) status were created by splitting out of their host *woredas*.

Nowadays, the number of *woreda* and *zonal* governments is continuously increasing while amalgamation and disappearance of existing local units has remained the exception.¹¹⁴ This local government practice has been the locus of state-society relations in the contemporary Ethiopian sub-national politics. Frequent demand has been coming from the local people claiming a new local government status. Despite the impression of the government is towards this frequent demand, the split of local governments remains a pressing issue in Ethiopia. The most significant recent trend of change in the figure of local government is the creation of new (special) *woredas* and (nationality) *zones* via the splitting of existing ones.

Splitting of *woredas* has been encouraged in order to meet two different objectives: (i) ensuring self-governments of ethnic groups and (ii) enhance development and public participation through decentralized governance system. The first motive and its implementation accelerated the claims of self-determination by many minority ethnic groups. This still is one of the pressing issues on the table of regional state executive offices. The splitting practices aimed to achieve the second goal are also accompanied by public requests. Many delegates of people have frequently appeared before the regional state executive office claiming new local government status and hoping to receive service in a more efficient and effective way.

¹¹¹ Solomon Nigussie, 'Intergovernmental Fiscal Arrangements in Ethiopia: Some Basic Issues' in Asnake Kefale and Assefa Fiseha (eds), *Federalism and Local Government in Ethiopia* (UNDP and Center for Federal Studies 2015) 99.

¹¹² Ayenew Birhanu, 'The Politics of Local Government Creation and Boundary Demarcation within Ethiopian Federation' (PhD thesis, Center for Federalism and Governance Studies, Addis Ababa University 2017) 116.

¹¹³ *ibid* 117.

¹¹⁴ *ibid* 120.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Birhanu A, 'The Politics of Local Government Creation and Boundary Demarcation within Ethiopian Federation' (PhD thesis, Center for Federalism and Governance Studies, Addis Ababa University 2017)

Nigussie S, 'Intergovernmental Fiscal Arrangements in Ethiopia: Some Basic Issues' in Asnake Kefale and Assefa Fiseha (eds), *Federalism and Local Government in Ethiopia* (UNDP and Center for Federal Studies 2015)

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

